

ELIXIR Community Database (ECD)

Process Version 1 - July, 2025

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ELIXIR Community Database Concept

Data resource visibility and co-development gap within ELIXIR

Through the [Core Data Resources \(CDR\)](#) and [ELIXIR Deposition Databases \(EDD\)](#) processes, ELIXIR peer reviews and accredits mature biodata resources based on several indicators and wide life-science community usage. However, there is a gap within ELIXIR as a life science data research infrastructure to support the visibility and co-development of its highly valuable biodata resources that serve a narrower scientific community. While some resources could become CDR, we acknowledge other resources may never scale to the eligibility scope of a CDR or EDD but serve specific [ELIXIR Community](#) needs.

ELIXIR Community Database process

As of July 2025, ELIXIR has 187 data resources on the [ELIXIR Service Delivery Plan \(SDP\)](#) but there is a much narrower portfolio of 32 CDR and 16 EDD, leaving a large gap for supporting the co-development and visibility of the remaining data resources, many of which may hold major relevance to ELIXIR Communities. In response, this document details a process for biodata resources on the ELIXIR SDP entitled **ELIXIR Community Database (ECD)**. The process has been developed by the [ELIXIR Data Platform](#) in close collaboration with the ELIXIR Community leads. It is designed to be ELIXIR Community & Data Platform driven and its purpose is to:

- Create stronger links between ELIXIR biodata resources and their target user Communities.
- Support maturation through Community driven co-development.
- Increase visibility of ELIXIR Community relevant databases to improve findability and use.
- Provide a formal status ELIXIR Community Database (ECD) status to biodata resources.

The ECD process involves six lightweight steps to be progress to ECD status:

[1. ELIXIR Service Delivery Plan Engagement](#)

[2. Self-assessment checklist](#)

[3. Hub eligibility check](#)

[4. ELIXIR Community decision process](#)

[5. One year health check period & accreditation](#)

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[Appendix 3: ECD Rejection Criteria](#)

Eligibility

The ECD process will support ELIXIR SDP biodata resources (non-CDR/EDD) to mature, and where a database develops sufficiently in specific areas, this ECD status would strengthen a candidate's future application for CDR/EDD accreditation. However, not all data resources are within the scope of CDR/EDD status, and a pathway to CDR/EDD status is not the primary purpose of the process.

1. ELIXIR Service Delivery Plan Engagement

1. The following information will be provided to Node leadership during their annual SDP update on both ELIXIR and global biodata resource accreditation and maturation processes:
 - a. **ELIXIR Community Databases** (this document)
 - b. [Core Data Resource](#) & [ELIXIR Deposition Database](#)
 - c. [Global Core Biodata Resource \(GCBR\)](#)
 - d. [CoreTrustSeal](#)
 - e. [EOSC FIDELIS - Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix \(TTRAM\)](#)
 - f. [RDA Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers](#)
2. The ECD process information provided to Nodes will include:

- a. Webpage with all ECD information centralised
 - b. ECD process document (this document)
 - c. ECD self-assessment checklist (the related ECD application form)
 - d. Hub contact points for ECD checklist submission, further information and support
3. During Node SDP updates, interest can be expressed to submit their ELIXIR SDP biodata resources by following this document's sections 2-6. However, the ECD process is planned to run on a rolling basis in collaboration with the Communities and interested existing SDP biodata resources will be the first candidates for the pilot ECD process.

2. Self-assessment checklist

The ECD self-assessment checklist is designed as a lightweight disclosure to support:

- [Hub eligibility check \(step 3\)](#) - basic information for participation assessed.
- [ELIXIR Community decision process \(step 4\)](#) - resource information assessed for eligibility.

The ECD checklist must be filled out by an applicant resource to apply to a single Community for ECD status and can be found:

- [On the ECD webpage](#)
- [On Zenodo](#)

It gathers key information on the resource leveraging many simple yes/no responses and also acts as a guide for resource providers to check if key resource maturity/best practice milestones have been achieved as an ELIXIR biodata resource such as:

- [FAIRsharing](#) resource registration
- [Identifiers.org](#) identifier registration
- +...

The checklist also collects information on which ELIXIR Community the resource intends to engage for ECD accreditation. After completion it must then be sent to:

elixir-community-databases@elixir-europe.org

This will then formally begin the ECD process.

3. Hub eligibility check

1. The self-assessment checklist is sent to the ELIXIR Hub Data Platform & Communities staff to do an initial eligibility check.
2. This includes lightweight practical checks such as:
 - a. Resource is a biological: deposition database / knowledgebase / registry / aggregation database
 - b. Is a resource containing data intended for European/international use
 - c. Resource is provided by an ELIXIR institute with a Node affiliation
 - d. Resource is included on an ELIXIR Node SDP
 - e. Resource does not currently hold the status of CDR/EDD/GCBR/RIR.
 - f. All sections are complete.

3. After the eligibility checks are completed, the self-assessment checklist application submitted for ECD status will be sent to the relevant ELIXIR Community Co-leads for which the biodata resource is applying to for decision on accreditation.

4. ELIXIR Community & Data Platform joint decision process

1. The ECD [self-assessment checklist \(section 2\)](#) will be provided to the ELIXIR Community Co-leads and Data Platform ExCo by the Hub staff after initial eligibility checks are passed.
2. The Community Co-leads and Data Platform ExCo upon receipt of the application will initiate the ECD decision process to evaluate suitability for ECD accreditation which should take no longer than 3 months.
 - a. They will assess the Scientific & Service Level criteria to ensure suitable. Note Appendix 3 ECD Rejection Criteria of breakdown of focus areas by the Community Leads & Data Platform Leadership.
3. The Hub Data Platform staff will act as contact points during the application evaluation process.
4. The process to evaluate and assess a biodata resource's ECD application will be at the discretion of the Community co-leads and Data Platform ExCo who will be responsible to jointly decide on the ECD application with a consensus joint decision.
 - i. If there is a conflict of interest (e.g. same Node as applicant resource), this will require delegation of the voting right to a non-conflicted Community member agreed upon by the Community co-leads.
5. Where any issues arise from during a decision process, the Hub ELIXIR Community & Data Platform contacts will assess any concerns raised.
6. The outcome of the Community's decision to provide ECD accreditation will be fed back to an applicant no later than 3 months from point of submission. The outcomes will be:

Successful: biodata resource selected for ECD accreditation by Community.

Unsuccessful: biodata resource not selected for ECD accreditation by Community.

In both cases feedback and further recommendations will be provided by the Community co-leads on the originally submitted self-assessment ECD application form.

7. Where an application is unsuccessful, re-application is possible after a period of 12 months provided sufficient changes have been implemented addressing failing criteria for ECD accreditation during the initial application. Where no significant change has been made the Hub eligibility check will not progress the application to ECD Community review.

Future considerations for ECD version 2 update:

- In version 1, the applicant biodata resource declares in the checklist which Community they are applying for ECD status accreditation from. A limit of one Community can be chosen to

be applied to and the biodata resource must be relevant to the Community topic to be considered for Community ECD review.

- A limit of one ECD application to a single Community is to be applied during the ECD pilot phase to ensure the process is viable and scalable.
- Where there is genuine benefit for a biodata resource to be considered for ECD engagement under further ELIXIR Communities, this will be assessed during the pilot phase and a clear process defined to handle this in the ECD version 2 process document.
- In version 1, during the pilot phase there is no limit on how many biodata resources can be ECD accredited by a Community.
 - However, where scalability for Communities is foreseen as an issue, this will be closely monitored and managed by the ELIXIR Hub & Community staff.
- Where there is no Community for a given resource biodata type, this will be monitored during the pilot phase. Including dissolution of a Community having given an ECD.

5. One year health check period & accreditation

1. From the point of successful Community ECD selection, the resource will be provided a provisional ECD status which can be displayed as a banner on the resource.
2. Alongside the provisional status a one year health check period will commence where simple uptime monitoring provided by the ELIXIR Hub (e.g. [NIH resource uptime dashboard](#), [Updown.io](#)) will be set up to ensure adequate resource uptime (e.g. 99%) during the first year. It is anticipated to have a centralised monitoring tool provisioned by the Hub.
3. During this period the Community will also be encouraged to establish engagement channels and co-development input mechanisms with the resource service providers such as on monthly calls or during annual F2F meetings. This may take shape as:
 - a. Providing advice on the resources development roadmap based on Community needs.
 - e.g. adopting interoperability standards and mechanisms to federate data between ELIXIR resources (API data sharing).
 - b. Support visibility of the resource in European & Global communities of relevance.
 - e.g. help link the service providers to relevant working groups, conferences and initiatives to avoid silos and federate to the wider biodata ecosystem.

A key focus will be ensuring any ECD is integratable into the ELIXIR and global biodata ecosystem to expand data interconnectivity.

4. After the one year health check (TBC exact periods) there will be two possible outcomes:
 - A. Full ECD status:** will be granted upon completion of the one year health check period where 99% uptime is met. This status will be valid for 3 years.
 - B. ECD provisional status revoked:** where uptime conditions are not met, the ECD provisional status will be removed and the biodata resource provider further engaged by the

ELIXIR Hub staff to determine the cause of the service provisioning issues and risk to the data.

6. Monitoring and Status Retention

1. A successful biodata resource will hold ECD status for a total of 3 years after passing the initial health check period.
2. After this point the resource will resubmit their ECD application to reflect key changes during the previous 3 year period. This will ensure the ECD portfolio is periodically monitored and in a healthy state.
 - a. The ECD document will be resubmitted and updated to reflect any changes.
 - b. The ECD document will undergo the same Community ECD review process.
3. Once a resource's resubmission for ECD is successful, a biodata resource will hold the status for a further 3 years (no health check period required).

Note: where a Community who has endorsed an ECD is disbanded before the next renewal this may barrier the possibility of a renewal without the existence of a supporting Community. While only a hypothetical this will be monitored through the case of what can be done for resources where there currently exists no relevant Community for them to apply to during the ECD pilot stage. This will be further discussed and addressed after the ECD pilot in the version 2 process.

Appendix 1: Acronym table

Acronym	Full Form
ECD	ELIXIR Community Database
CDR	Core Data Resource
EDD	ELIXIR Deposition Database
SDP	Service Delivery Plan
GCBR	Global Core Biodata Resource
EOSC FIDELIS	European Open Science Cloud - FIDELIS project
TTRAM	Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix
RIR	Recommended Interoperability Resource

Appendix 2: Synergies to wider initiatives

Accreditation processes:

ELIXIR Service Delivery Plan (SDP): A prerequisite to be on the ELIXIR SDP for ECD eligibility. The ELIXIR Service Delivery Plan (SDP) is simply the formal listing of services and resources provisioned officially by ELIXIR Node institutes. The ECD process goes further by providing formal accreditation, community-driven co-development pathway, and enhanced visibility specifically for those SDP biodata resources that are not yet, or may never be, Core Data Resources (CDR) or ELIXIR Deposition Databases (EDD).

CDR (Core Data Resources): While the ECD process aims to support the maturation and visibility of ELIXIR Community-specific biodata resources that serve narrower scientific communities. In contrast, ELIXIR Core Data Resources (CDRs) are identified as being of fundamental importance and generic value to the *wider* life-science community, undergoing a rigorous evaluation for long-term preservation, high scientific quality, and broad applicability. While an ECD status could strengthen a candidate's future application for CDR, it is explicitly not the primary purpose, as CDRs cater to a much broader user base and are considered authoritative in their fields. Ineligible CDR applications may be advised to apply for ECD application.

EDD (ELIXIR Deposition Databases): The ECD process supports ELIXIR Service Delivery Plan biodata resources to mature and increase their visibility within specific ELIXIR Communities. ELIXIR Deposition Databases (EDDs), in contrast, are a peer reviewed portfolio of recommended

repositories specifically for the *deposition of experimental data* from the international community, ensuring long-term data preservation and accessibility. While both involve data resources, EDDs are focused on providing guidance to users on resources to use for data sharing and archiving, whereas ECD is about fostering active co-development and promoting resources tailored to particular ELIXIR Community needs.

CoreTrustSeal: CoreTrustSeal is an international certification for trustworthy digital repositories, focusing on long-term preservation and access. The ECD process, while aiming to improve resource quality and findability, is an ELIXIR-internal initiative that supports maturation and Community engagement for resources serving specific ELIXIR needs, and it is not a direct substitute for the rigorous, globally recognised CoreTrustSeal certification.

Global Core Biodata Resource (GCBR): The Global Core Biodata Resource (GCBR) initiative identifies and supports biodata resources of global importance. The ECD process, while aiming to elevate valuable resources, is a more localised ELIXIR-internal framework focused on resources serving specific ELIXIR Community needs, which may not necessarily reach the global impact or scale of a GCBR. GCBR has a focus on funder engagement which is not within the scope of the ECD process.

RIR (Recommended Interoperability Resources): The ELIXIR Recommended Interoperability Resources (RIRs) are identified as key tools and registries that actively facilitate the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles across scientific research, particularly by supporting connections, metadata exposure, and infrastructure for integratable data collections within the broader ELIXIR ecosystem. While the ECD process encourages integrability and interoperability for its accredited resources, its primary focus is on formalising the status and supporting the community-driven co-development and increased visibility of biodata resources that serve narrower, specific ELIXIR Community needs, rather than a direct focus on core interoperability enablement as services.

Biodatabase relevant maturation processes:

EOSC FIDELIS - TTRAM: The ECD process primarily focuses on elevating the visibility and fostering co-development of ELIXIR Community-specific biodata resources. FIDELIS - TTRAM, on the other hand, provides a broader framework for assessing and promoting trustworthy repository attributes, which is a wider concern for data sustainability and reusability across disciplines, rather than solely within ELIXIR's Community scope.

Research Data Alliance (RDA) Trustworthy Repository Standards and Practice (TRSP): The Research Data Alliance (RDA) Trustworthy Repository Standards and Practice (TRSP) group aims to identify and promote best practices for trustworthy data repositories. The ECD process, in contrast, is an ELIXIR-specific mechanism designed to foster the growth and visibility of biodata resources within its own Communities, leveraging community expertise for co-development rather than focusing on broad repository standards.

EOSC Interoperability framework: The EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) Interoperability Framework provides guidelines and standards to ensure data and services can be seamlessly

exchanged across the EOSC ecosystem. The ECD process, conversely, is an ELIXIR-specific accreditation designed to increase the visibility and foster the co-development of biodata resources relevant to ELIXIR's communities, often with an emphasis on improving their integrability within the broader biodata ecosystem, but not directly defining the overarching interoperability framework.

EHDS/Data Spaces: The European Health Data Space (EHDS) and broader Data Spaces initiatives aim to create secure and interoperable data ecosystems for specific domains, like health. The ECD process, while potentially contributing data resources to such spaces, is an ELIXIR-internal mechanism focused on accrediting and supporting specific biodata resources for their value to ELIXIR's scientific communities, rather than defining the broader legal or technical frameworks for data sharing across sectors.

Overview table:

Initiative	Primary Focus	Scope / Audience	Key Differentiator from ECD
ELIXIR Community Database (ECD)	Formal accreditation, community-driven co-development, and enhanced visibility for niche databases.	Biodata resources serving narrower, specific ELIXIR Community needs.	This is the baseline for comparison.
ELIXIR Service Delivery Plan (SDP)	A formal listing of all services officially provided by ELIXIR Nodes.	All official ELIXIR Node services and resources.	An SDP listing is a prerequisite for ECD; it is a list, not an accreditation process.
Core Data Resource (CDR)	Identifying resources of fundamental importance and broad applicability to the life sciences.	The wider, generic life-science community.	CDRs are authoritative for a broad audience, while ECDs are tailored to narrower Community needs.
ELIXIR Deposition Database (EDD)	Recommending repositories for the deposition and archiving of experimental data.	Researchers needing to deposit and share experimental data.	EDD focuses on data deposition, whereas ECD focuses on active resource co-development.
CoreTrustSeal	International certification for trustworthy digital repositories focusing on long-term preservation.	Any digital repository seeking a globally recognised certification.	CoreTrustSeal is a rigorous, global certification, while ECD is a more lightweight, ELIXIR-internal initiative.
Global Core Biodata Resource (GCBR)	Identifying and supporting biodata resources of global importance, with a focus on funder engagement.	Biodata resources with a global scale and impact.	GCBR has a global scope and a focus on funders, unlike ECD's more localized, ELIXIR-Community scope.
Recommended Interoperability Resource (RIR)	Identifying key tools and registries that actively facilitate FAIR principles and data integration.	Services that enable interoperability across the ecosystem.	RIRs are services that enable interoperability, while ECDs are biodata resources that serve a specific Community.

EOSC FIDELIS - TTRAM	A framework for assessing trustworthy repository attributes across many disciplines.	Data sustainability and reusability across multiple scientific disciplines.	TTRAM is a broad, cross-disciplinary framework, not specific to ELIXIR's biodata Communities.
RDA TRSP	Promoting general best practices and standards for trustworthy data repositories.	Any data repository looking to adopt broad standards.	RDA focuses on broad repository standards, while ECD is an ELIXIR-specific mechanism for co-development.
EOSC Interoperability Framework	Providing the overarching guidelines and standards for data exchange across the entire EOSC ecosystem.	The European Open Science Cloud ecosystem.	This is a high-level framework for a massive ecosystem, not a specific accreditation process like ECD.
EHDS / Data Spaces	Creating secure and interoperable data ecosystems (e.g., for health) governed by legal and technical frameworks.	Broad data sharing across sectors, such as European health data.	These initiatives define broad legal/technical frameworks, whereas ECD is an internal mechanism to accredit specific scientific resources.

Appendix 3: ECD Rejection Criteria

Rejection Criteria

Based on the provided ECD checklist and process documents, an application can be rejected based on two levels of criteria: **administrative & service criteria**, which are checked by the ELIXIR Hub and lead to immediate disqualification, and **scientific & technical criteria**, which are assessed by the ELIXIR Community and may lead to a discretionary rejection. Additionally, a resource may be rejected due to a failed **health check criteria** for uptime of lower than 99% during the health check period.

Administrative Rejection Criteria (Hub Eligibility Check)

If a resource fails any of the following checks, its application **will not proceed** to the Community for review.

- **Incorrect Resource Type:** The service is not a deposition database, curated knowledgebase, biodata registry, or aggregation database.
- **No ELIXIR Affiliation:** The applicant is not from an ELIXIR Node institute and the resource is not an official ELIXIR Node Service listed on the Service Delivery Plan (SDP).
- **Existing High-Level Status:** The resource already holds a status as a Core Data Resource (CDR), ELIXIR Deposition Database (EDD), or Global Core Biodata Resource (GCBR).
- **Incomplete Application:** The applicant has not completed all fields in the checklist.

Scientific & Service Level Rejection Criteria

(Community & Data Platform Leadership Assessment)

Even if a resource passes the Hub check, the accrediting ELIXIR Community may still reject the application based on weaknesses identified in the self-assessment. These factors suggest the resource is not sufficiently mature, actively sustained, or relevant for ECD status.

Relevance and Uniqueness - Community Co-Leads

- **Lack of Relevance:** The resource has no clear relevance to the scientific focus area of the ELIXIR Community it is applying to. This is a major reason for rejection, as the entire process is community-driven.
- **No Identifiable Gap:** The application fails to demonstrate what unique scientific gap the resource serves, or it is entirely redundant with existing resources without offering any clear advantage.

Sustainability and Governance - Hub & Data Platform ExCo

- **No Staffing:** The resource lacks any dedicated staffing for curation and maintenance or to provide the necessary hardware to keep it online for at least the next three years.
- **High Risk of Discontinuation:** The project is critically dependent on just one single individual, meaning it would likely cease development or data ingestion if they were to leave.
- **Lack of Governance:** There is no evidence of a development roadmap, a scientific advisory board, or a mechanism to collect user feedback to guide future work.

Interoperability and Data Management - Hub & Data Platform ExCo

- **Creates a Data Silo:** The resource does not use any metadata standards or ontologies and does not provide an API or other machine-actionable way to access the data. This goes against the ECD goal of reducing database silos.
- **Restrictive or Unclear Licensing:** The data and software licenses are not clearly stated, are missing, or are restrictive, which prevents the data from being reused by the community.
- **Poor Data Management:** The resource has no clear plan for long-term data storage and off-site backups, posing a significant risk to data integrity and longevity.

Health Check Failure Rejection Criteria

(Community & Data Platform Leadership Assessment)

- **Uptime Failure:** Validated uptime falling below 99% as recorded by the Hub tracker during the set probation period. Period will be indicated during the process set up.

Step after the rejection for possible reapplication:

1. Applicant is informed of rejection and specific feedback provided on the application form to inform the applicant what exactly needs to be addressed by the resource for a successful reapplication (where resource within Community scope).
2. Reapplication where deemed suitable under agreement of meeting the Community's scientific focus area is possible 12 months after the initial application. The feedback must be addressed adequately to be considered for reapplication.